

Received: 08 Jun 2020/ Accepted: 12 Mar 2021/ Published: 31 May 2021
 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4876598>

A Comprehensive Study on Extraction, Characterization and Fabrication of Natural Fiber - Polymer Composites & Nano-Composites

Shivanshu Dixit^{1*}, R K Mishra²

¹Indian Institute of Technology Ropar, Rupnagar, Punjab, India, 140001

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, Shri Mata Vaishno Devi University, Katra, Jammu and Kashmir, India, 182320
 Corresponding author: Shivanshu Dixit (shivanshud36@gmail.com)

This work was presented at the International Conference on Natural Polymers (ICNP-2019) held during 6-8, December 2019 at Mahatma Gandhi University, Kottayam, Kerala, India.

Abstract: With the advances in material science and process engineering, environment-friendly and biodegradable materials are gaining a lot of popularity and usability. A four-fold increase is seen in areas of R&D's and industries in terms of bio-friendly materials. Particularly, when composite materials are appreciated as an alternative to conventional engineering materials, natural fiber-reinforced composite (NFRC) has the edge over synthetic fibers reinforced composites (FRC) in terms of biocompatibility and environmental concerns. Some handpick advantages like low density, natural abundance, economical, least environmental impact, and versatile application potentials make NFRC's viable in many fields. However, moisture absorption and poor fiber-matrix interface are some hiccups in the development and performance of NFRC's. While efforts are made by both industries and researchers in the escalation of mechanical performance and structural capabilities for such materials, this review aims to provide an overview of the NFRC material. The study expance included here is the process of extracting natural fibers from the source, physical-mechanical properties of these fibers, and their selection. NFRC's- matrix types, composite fabrication, the response in static and dynamic conditions, mechanical strength, electrical and thermal properties, etc. are included in this review. Aspects of NFRC nanocomposite is also covered here in this article. NFRC and nano-NFRC biomaterials have the potential to equalize in terms of structural material used in a variety of sectors like household structures, construction, automobile, aerospace, biotechnology, while the scope of improvement and applicability of such biocomposite needs more attention.

Extraction of natural fibers from plant

Natural fiber fiber reinforcement polymer composite

SEM images of Cotton fibers

Key words: Natural fibre, Composite, Bio-degradability, Nano-composite, Fiber extraction

References

1. Jawaid MH, Khalil HA. Cellulosic/synthetic fibre reinforced polymer hybrid composites: A review. Carbohydrate polymers. 2011 Aug 1;86(1):1-8.
2. Jawaid M, Khalil HA, Bakar AA. Woven hybrid composites: Tensile and flexural properties of oil palm-woven jute fibres based epoxy composites. Materials Science and Engineering: A. 2011 Jun 15;528(15):5190-5.
3. Fahmy TY, Mobarak F. Nanocomposites from natural cellulose fibers filled with kaolin in presence of sucrose. Carbohydrate Polymers. 2008 Jun 10;72(4):751-5.
4. Pickering KL, Efendy MA, Le TM. A review of recent developments in natural fibre composites and their mechanical performance. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing. 2016 Apr 1;83:98-112.

